

PSYCHOLOGICAL - PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF HEALTHY NUTRITION OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION STUDENTS.

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Abstract

In this article, the concepts of promoting the formation of healthy eating skills in preschool educational organizations, which are carried out consistently in different directions, based on a specific program, in specific directions, in particular, concepts about impact on the human body of the formation of healthy eating skills in preschool educational organizations, first of all, in the process of pedagogical education, giving children certain medical and hygienic knowledge about the formation of healthy eating skills, the formation of healthy eating skills in children, are highlighted.

Promotion of the formation of healthy eating skills in preschool educational organizations should be carried out consistently in different directions, based on a specific program, in specific directions. In particular, it is focused on providing children with certain medical and hygienic knowledge regarding the formation of healthy eating skills in the pedagogical education process, and on the formation of concepts about the impact of the formation of healthy eating skills on the improvement of the human body, on the other hand, in children following hygienic rules based on a strict regimen is directly related to forming the skills to turn health care of oneself and others into a daily habit.

Psychologists have identified the characteristics of children in the first years of life, which determine their maximum sensitivity to education and training. Such characteristics include plasticity of high nervous and mental activity, imitation and suggestibility, emotionality. The uniqueness of home education is explained, first of all, by its priority, special importance in the life of the child due to the biological and psychological connection of close adults. The upbringing process is optimized due to the development of valuable needs in the baby, which are communication, receiving new impressions (in later knowledge), active motor activity, recognition, love and etc.

From the first days of a child's life, the world of people, nature and things surrounds him. However, not all adults and all environments are conducive to a child's development from birth. A child who is separated from his parents (often abandoned by them) and placed in a children's home, the general mental tone decreases, emotional-cognitive interactions deteriorate, and as a result, intellectual development slows down. The sooner the child is separated from the parental family, the longer and longer he is in the children's home, the more obvious the deformations in all areas of his mental development (I. Langmeer, Z. Mateichik, S. Meshcheryakova, V. Mukhina, E. Smirnova and others).

Psychological-pedagogical studies show that (A. Leontiev, S. Kozlova, etc.) the whole diversity of the surrounding world, which affects a small child in one way or another, the "intimate social circle" have particular importance (A. Leontiev). This circle includes the parents and other close people who protect, love, and emotionally imprint the baby, sometimes for a lifetime. The child is ready to actively use this image very early: even in the pre-speech period (A. Zaporozhets, A. Kosheleva, Ya. Neverovich). If the baby is desired and loved, and his relatives spread love and affection, he is especially sensitive to their educational influence. On the contrary, in the first years of life, the child does not accept the words, persuasions and advice of the "stranger" (for example, travelers in transport, pedagogues of other groups).

Therefore, as the first and very important factor determining the special importance of family upbringing in the formation of a child's personality, making it a priority compared to other educational organizations (preschool education organization, school, orphanage, etc.), scientists deeply emotional, sincere nature family education. It is built on the basis of kinship and its "guides" are parents' love for children and children's mutual feelings for parents (connection, trust, affection) (Y. Azarov, I. Grebennikov, T. Markova, A. Petrovsky, A. Kharchev and others).

However, this is not the only factor that ensures the effectiveness, strength and stability of family education. In the study of T. Markova, we find a rationale for two more factors:

influence of mother, father, other family members in different life situations, their repetition from day to day;
availability of objective opportunities to involve children in household, economic, educational activities of the family.

A family, a small group, a kind of "microcosm", most fully meets the requirements of the child's gradual introduction into social life and the gradual

expansion of his worldview and experience. At the same time, it should be taken into account that the family is not a homogeneous, but a differentiated social group. It provides different ages (older and younger members of the family), gender (men and women) and sometimes by profession (mother is a musician, father is a doctor, grandmother is a pedagogue, grandfather is a biologist) "subsystems". This allows the child to show his abilities to the widest extent, to realize his needs faster and more fully (Y.Azarov, I.Grebennikov, A.Kharchev). Thus, modern science has information that the family is the first and most important educational organization in human life .

At 70s of XX century and at the beginning of the 80s, some aspects of education were studied, for example, "Raising the beginning of discipline in children of preschool age in the family" by N. Starodubova, "The game as a means of moral upbringing of a preschool child in the family" directing behavior in older preschool children L. Zagik, "Pedagogical conditions for teaching children of senior preschool age to work in the family" D. Dzinter.

From the point of view of the interaction of the kindergarten and the family in raising children and helping parents, V. Bezlyudnaya's "Interaction of the preschool educational organization and the family in the pedagogical correction of relations between preschool children and peers" information, interest obtained in the work. The author convincingly shows that neither the family nor the pre-school education organization can separately solve the problem of eliminating deviations in the relationship with peers related to the child's nutrition and education in the family. As a result of the implemented experimental work, there were positive changes in the nature of relations between pedagogues and parents, and in the attitude of peers towards their children.

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